

**PHYTOMACROFAUNA AND HEAVY METAL CONCENTRATION OF WATER FROM A
TIDAL CREEK IN SOUTH-WESTERN NIGERIA**

Okunade G.F.

Department of Biological Sciences, Yaba College of Tech

Abstract

The community structure of phytomacrobenthos and heavy metal concentration of water from a tidal creek in south-western Nigeria were examined for a period of six months (January,2023-June,2023). Four major classes in this study, (Crustacea, Insecta, Gastropoda and Polychaeta) and eight taxa were identified from a total of 175 individuals collected from the five stations. The most abundant organism found in all stations was species of *Exocirrolana sp.* *Penaeus sp* and *Littorina sp.* Were also abundant but their occurrence was affected by seasonal variation. *Nereis sp.* was the only polychaete recorded throughout the study. The concentrations of Iron, Zinc, Manganese, Cadmium, Chromium and Lead in water were determined by Atomic Absorption Spectrophotometer (AAS). The Iron concentration varied between 0.11 to 0.752 (0.24725 ± 0.119577); Zinc values, 0.004 to 0.014 (0.00716 ± 0.00235); Manganese 0.005 to 0.019 (0.009458 ± 0.004201); Nickel, 0.003 to 0.018 (0.007417 ± 0.004602); Copper, 0.003 to 0.02 (0.00716 ± 0.0044); cadmium, 0.002 to 0.012mg/l and the concentrations of Chromium were less than 0.01 (<0.01) at all stations through the period of study.

Key words: *Heavy metals, phytomacrobenthos, tidal creek*

INTRODUCTION AND LITERATURE REVIEW

Over the years, tidal creeks are known to be fertile coastal environment used as feeding and nursery grounds by a large number of fishes and aquatic crustaceans (1). Furthermore, Creeks in this region are usually connected to lagoons and find their way to the sea via the Lagos harbor all year round (2). Heavy metals are high priority pollutants because of their relative high toxicity and persistent nature in the environment. However, there is a significant paucity of records on sustained and coordinated measurement of levels of heavy metals of identifiable sampling points. By virtue of its position, the Abule-Eledu creek within the Lagos lagoon is surrounded by densely populated and human domestic wastes. Recently, Onyema and Nwankwo (3) reported tidal creek ecosystems, particularly in the industrialized areas of Lagos metropolis are enduring stress-induced changes as a result of steadily yet increasing human activities and associated effects. Unregulated, unrestricted and direct deposition of wastes and human faecal droppings is key to most of these imposed human effects. At present in south western Nigeria, many water bodies are enriched by indiscriminate waste disposal (4; 5) which encourages the growth of nuisance species of algae (6) that cause mortality of aquatic fauna and reduce the use of surface waters. (7) Reported that variability of water quality influences the toxicity levels of heavy metals on estuarine organisms as it affects the physical and chemical composition of the ecosystem. Heavy metals are high priority pollutants because of their relative high toxicity and persistent nature in the environment. Toxicity of heavy metals depends of kind of metal, compound, from the amount which is deposited in organism and from time extension action of metal (8). Most investigations of heavy metals concentration in Nigeria have focused on occasional determination of the types and concentrations of such metals in industrial effluents (9) and some segment of the ecosystem particularly sediment and water column (10,11)

This paper presents the results of the investigation of the benthic phytomacrofauna and heavy metal contents of water from a tidal creek in south-western Nigeria.

.MATERIALS AND METHODS
DESCRIPTION OF STUDY AREA

The Abule-Eledu creek, situated within the University of Lagos (Brackish water creek) forms part of the many sluggish tidal creeks that drain into the Lagos lagoon. The creek is shallow ($\leq 1\text{m}$), tidal and sheltered. It is fed by water from the adjoining Lagos lagoon at high tide, and at low tide the water ebbs into the lagoon. Its harbors many aquatic macrophytes which at certain times of the year completely cover the water surface and affect navigation of canoe. The creek meanders through a riparian mangrove swamp which is inundated at high tide and partially exposed at low tide. Notable riparian flora of the creek includes *Paspalum orbiculare*, *Eichhornia crassipes*, *Acrotiscum aureum*, *Phoenix reclinata*, *Rhizophora racemosa*, *Avicenia nitida*,. Notable fauna includes *Balanus pallidus*, *uca tangeri*, *Seserma huzardi*, and *Tympanotomus fuscatus*. The creek is located in south-western Nigeria and hence exposed to two distinct seasons, the wet (May-October) and dry season (November-April) (12) and this season has effect on the availability of macrophytes.

Figure 1: Map of Abule-Eledu creek (Lagos lagoon) showing the Sampling stations

Laboratory Procedures: The concentrations of iron (Fe), zinc (Zn), manganese (Mn), cadmium (Cd), chromium (Cr) and lead (Pb) in the samples of water were determined with Atomic Absorption Spectrophotometer (AAS). The wave lengths used for measurements were 213.9 nm for Zn, 220 nm for Mn, 228.8 nm for Cd, 214.5 nm for Cr and 217.0 nm for Pb with detection limits of 48, 35, 32, 15, 24 and 41 µg/L, respectively. Data provided were the average of three replicates. The analyses were executed by SPSS (version 9) package. The values of these parameters were compared to the WHO standard for unpolluted or clean water.

Sample analyses

In the laboratory, macroinvertebrate samples were washed to remove the fixative and sorted under a dissecting microscope. Specimens of macroinvertebrates were identified to the lowest possible taxonomic level using the available keys of (13), (14) and (15).

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Physical and Chemical Parameters: The results of physical and chemical parameters of water samples from the four stations in the Abule-Eledu creek of Lagos lagoon are presented in Table 1.

	Station 1			Station 2			Station 3			Station 4		
	MEAN±SD	MI N	MA X	MEAN ± SD	MI N	M AX	MEAN ± SD	MI N	M AX	MEAN ± SD	MI N	M AX
Parameter												
Air temperature (°C)	28.66 ± 2.50	24	31	28.5 ± 2.56	24.5	32	28.66 ± 1.59	26	31	30.33 ± 2.42	28	34
Water temperature (°C)	28.66 ± 1.03	28	30	27.91 ± 2.90	23	31.5	27.53 ± 3.20	22	32	29.08 ± 1.56	27.5	32
Copper (mg/L)	0.007 ± 0.006	0.03	0.019	0.008 ± 0.006	0.02	0.09	0.006 ± 0.0024	0.04	0.011	0.006 ± 0.02	0.03	0.009
Iron (mg/L)	0.28 ± 0.23	0.11	0.752	0.21 ± 0.03	0.18	0.26	0.26 ± 0.05	0.21	0.367	0.23 ± 0.03	0.2	0.28
Zinc (mg/L)	0.007 ± 0.001	0.06	0.008	0.0076 ± 0.003	0.06	0.05	0.006 ± 0.0018	0.01	0.07	0.007 ± 0.002	0.04	0.012
Cadmiu	0.007 ±	<	0.00	0.007 ±	<	0.0	0.007 ±	0.0	0.0	0.007 ±	<	0.00

m (mg/L)	0.003	0.0 3	8	0.003	0.0 3	08	0.0042	02	11	0.002	0.0 03	9
Lead (mg/L)	0.005 ± 0	< 0.0 01	0.00 05	0.007± 0	<0. 01	0.0 07	0.003 ±00	...	0.0 03	0.0095 ± 0.0063	<0. 01	0.01 4
Chromi um (mg/L)	0.01 ± 0	<0. 01	0	0 ±0	<0. 01	<0. 01	0 ± 0	<0. 01	<0.0 1
Mangan ese (mg/L)	0.011 ±0.005	0.0 06	0.01 9	0.009 ± 0.004	0.0 05	0.0 1	0.009 ± 0.0046	0.0 05	0.0 18	0.008 ±0.0021	0.0 05	0.01 1
Nickel (mg/L)	0.008 ±0.0049	<0. 01	0.01 4	0.009 ± 0.007	<0. 01	0.0 18	0.007 ± 0.004	0.0 03	0.0 11	0.005 ±0.0011	<0. 01	0.00 6
Chlorop hyll a (µg/L)	12.56 ± 4.11	18	8.9	10.28 ± 1.92	8.8	14	10.03 ±1.62	8.5	12	10.31 ± 2.87	8	16

HEAVY METALS

ZINC (Zn)

The zinc level ranged from 0.004 to 0.014mg/L. The highest (0.014mg/L) value was recorded in January while the lowest (0.004) value occurred in May. The mean zinc value for the sampling duration was 0.0071 while the standard deviation was ± 0.0023

IRON (Fe)

The iron level ranged from 0.11 to 0.752mg/L. The highest value was recorded in January while the lowest value occurred in May. The highest sets of value were recorded in January while there was a sharp decline from February to June. The mean iron value for the sampling duration was 0.24725 while the standard deviation was ± 0.1195

COPPER (Cu)

The copper level ranged from 0.003 to 0.020mg/L. The highest value was recorded in the month of June in station 2 while the lowest value occurred in May in station 1. The mean copper value for the sampling duration was 0.00716 while the standard deviation was ± 0.00442

CADMIUM (Cd)

The cadmium level ranged from 0.002 to 0.012mg/L. The highest (0.012) value was recorded in April in station 3 while the lowest (0.002) value occurred in January. The mean cadmium value for the sampling duration was 0.0075 while the standard deviation was ± 0.003141

LEAD (Pb)

Station 4 recorded the highest concentration of lead (0.014 mg/L) in June, while the lowest concentration (<0.01 mg/L) was recorded in almost every station. The mean salinity value for the sampling duration was 0.0068 while the standard deviation was ± 0.004266

CHROMIUM (Cr)

The lowest concentration of chromium (<0.01 mg/L) was recorded at every station throughout the duration of this study.

MANGANESE (Mn)

The lowest concentration of manganese (0.005) was recorded in station 3 in the month of January while the highest concentration (0.019) was in station 1 in the month of June. The mean manganese value for the sampling duration was 0.009458 while the standard deviation was ± 0.004201

NICKEL (mg/L)

The highest concentration of Nickel (0.0018mg/L) was recorded in station 2 in the month of January while the lowest (0.003) was recorded in June in station 4. However, a very low concentration (<0.01mg/L) was recorded throughout the duration of this study. The mean nickel value for the sampling duration was 0.00741 while the standard deviation was ±0.0046.

CHLOROPHYLL *a* (µg/L)

Chlorophyll *a* concentration ranged from 8.8µg/L recorded in February to 18mg/L recorded in March. The mean chlorophyll value for the sampling duration was 10.8 while the standard deviation was ±2.82.

Rainfall: Data on rainfall during the study period fluctuated between 0mm and 317.4 mm. The highest rain (460.9 mm) was recorded in May while the lowest (0mm) was in January. The highest rain fall was recorded (317.4 mm.) The mean rainfall for the period of study was 137.3333 ±135.6453.

Fig 2: Monthly variation in Manganese at the Abule -Eledu creek (January 2023- June 2023)

Fig 3: Monthly variation in Zinc at the Abule -Eledu creek (January 2023- June 2023)

Fig 4: Monthly variation in Iron at the Abule -Eledu creek (January 2023- June 2023)

Fig 5: Monthly variation in Copper at the Abule -Eledu creek (January 2023- June 2023)

COMMUNITY STRUCTURE OF BENTHIC PHYTOMACROFAUNA

Phytoplankton infaunal were collected at the study stations monthly within the Abule-Eledu creek (Lagos lagoon area) in south western part of Nigeria. A total of 175 individuals were obtained throughout the study period. They belong to three phyla: Mollusca, Arthropoda and Annelida and three classes: Crustacea, Insecta, Gastropoda and Polychaeta. Four species Crustacea were collected namely *Seserma sp*, *Nymphula sp*, *penaeus*, *Exocirolana* and while Insecta was represented by *Belostoma sp*. Two species of Gastropoda were collected namely *Turritella sp*.and *Littorina sp*. one species of polychaeta namely *Nereis sp*. Ecological indices were computed and the results shown in Table 4 with the number and classification of the fauna collected. The most abundant organism found in all stations was species of *Exocirolana sp*.

TABLE 1: OVERALL PERCENTAGE COMPOSITION

PHYLUM	NO OF INDIVIDUALS	CLASSES	FAMILIES	TOTAL NO OF INDIVIDUALS	OVERALL COMPOSITION
ARTHROPODA	138	2	4	175	79%
MOLLUSCA	30	1	2	175	17%
ANNELIDA	7	1	1	175	4%

Fig 6: Overall percentage composition of Phytomacrofauna

DISCUSSION

The quality of an aquatic ecosystem depends on environmental factors, which in turn can influence the structuring of aquatic communities. Therefore, it is usually desirable to identify these environmental factors (16). A total of 175 individuals were obtained throughout the study period. They belong to three phyla: Mollusca, Arthropoda and Annelida and three classes: Crustacea, Insecta, Gastropoda and Polychaeta. Four species of Crustacea were collected namely *Seserma sp*, *Nymphula sp*, *penaeus*, *Exocirolana* and while Insecta was represented by *Belostoma sp*. Two species of Gastropoda were collected namely *Turritella sp* and *Littorina sp*. one species of polychaeta namely *Nereis sp*. *Exocirolana sp*, *Penaeus sp* and *Littorina sp*. were more abundant species but their occurrence was affected by seasonal variation *Nereis sp*. was the only polychaete recorded. Arthropods were the most abundant; they contributed 138 individuals, constituting 79% of the total population of phytomacrofauna. However, The taxa recorded in this study is lower than that reported by (17) for phytomacrofauna arthropod community in the same lagoon and for phytomacrofauna communities in a non – tidal creek in south-western Nigeria, respectively, and that recorded by (18).

The taxonomic knowledge of African fresh water fauna is generally low and thus has limited the identification of some of the individual to the generic level, (19). At all stations, arthropods, were the most abundant phyla associated with the roots of water hyacinth in the study stretch. This is an indication that the plant is either being used as habitat for epibenthic macroinvertebrates, (20, 21), Some of the dominant molluscs encountered during the study are endemic to West Africa and the total numbers of individuals are characteristic of plant morphology. Water hyacinth is a very good habitat for Molluscs, (22) and accounted for the observed population in the hyacinth mat.

A class of annelids was recorded which confirms that the physical and chemical qualities of water and the immediate substrate for attachment, anthropogenic activities and food availability could have acted as important factors affecting the abundance of macrobenthic invertebrates, (23). All heavy metals analyzed in this study were detected in water, the mean value of Iron, Lead, Copper, Zinc, Nickel, Manganese, Chromium, and Cadmium in water samples from the four sampling stations are below the FEPA/WHO threshold limits of 1.000mg/l, 3.000mg/l and 2.000mg/l respectively. Although heavy metals in aquatic environment are from natural sources (soil formation), non point sources, transportation, domestic wastes, urban run-off, Agricultural practices and industries. Industrial activities such as industrial effluent discharge have been reported as a major contributing factor (24, 25, 26). Metal are reported to be well concentrated in the water (27,28) and sediments (29 and 30). Bioaccumulation of these metals in many fish species and their organs have been variously reported by (31), (32), (33),and (34).

The Zinc values of 0.004 to 0.014 (0.00716 ± 0.00235) with the highest value recorded in January (station 2) while the lowest was recorded in may (station 4). Zn is an enzyme co-factor in several enzyme systems including carbonic anhydrase found in red blood cells. Its toxicity to fish according to (35) and (36) can be greatly influenced by both water hardness and pH. It is one of the earliest known

trace metals and a common environmental pollutant, which is widely distributed in the aquatic environment.

The Cd concentrations in this study varied from 0.002 in station 4 (May) and 0.014 in station 2 (January). Sources of Cd in water include weathering of minerals and soils, discharge of domestic effluents and urban storm-water runoff containing Cd-laden materials. The possible accumulation of Cd in man is mainly in the kidney and liver. Its high concentrations lead to chronic kidney dysfunction, inducing cell injury and death by interfering with calcium (Ca) regulation in biological systems in man, fish and other aquatic organisms (36). The Concentrations of Cadmium (Cd) in large amount constitute a serious health hazard. Cd is very soluble in water and it is important in several enzyme systems. Cd is one of the most toxic elements with widespread carcinogenic effects in humans (36). It is widely distributed in the aquatic environment.

The Lead values of 0.003 to 0.014 (0.0068 ± 0.00426) with the highest value recorded in June (station 4) while the lowest was recorded in January (station 3). Most values recorded were however less than 0.01 (<0.01). Ingestion of lead can post a series health risk to humans. For Adults, lead exposure is usually limited to certain occupational and recreational sources. In babies and children, exposure to lead in drinking water above the action level can result in delays in physical and mental development, along with slight deficits in attention span and learning abilities. Most of the metals are introduced into the lagoon system through industrial processes, sewage disposal, soil leaching and rainfall.

The Manganese (Mn) concentrations in water in this study ranged from 0.005 to 0.019 (0.009458 ± 0.004201) with the highest value recorded in June (station 2) and lowest in January (station 3). Though there were variations across the stations that were not significantly different. The Mn levels from this study were below the recommended or acceptable level for unpolluted water. The recommended MCL for Mn in water is 0.05 mg/l (37). Mn in nature is found in form of oxides, silicates and carbonates. It functions as co-factor in the synthesis of urea from ammonia, amino acid and fatty acid metabolism and glucose oxidation. Inhalation of high dose of Mn leads to death. Mn is an element of low toxicity having considerable biological significance and one of the more biogeochemical and active transition metals in aquatic environment (38).

In this study the concentrations of Chromium were less than 0.01 (<0.01) at all stations through the period of study. These values were lower than the maximum contaminant level (MCL) of 0.1 mg/l recommended by (37) for unpolluted water. The Iron (Fe) concentrations in water from the Abule-Eledu creek varied between 0.11 to 0.752 (0.24725 ± 0.119577) However, 0.3 - 1.0 mg/l are satisfactory level but may cause staining and objectionable taste.

Fe values of $1.0 >$ are unsatisfactory in drinking water. Fe is an important metal in both plants and animals, especially in the cellular processes (39). The Nickel (Ni) concentration in water from the Abule-Eledu creek varied between 0.003 to 0.018 (0.007417 ± 0.004602) with the lowest value recorded in June (stations 2 and 3) while the highest was recorded in January (station 2). Most values recorded were however less than 0.01 (<0.01). The concentrations of copper in this study ranged between 0.003

to 0.02 (0.00716 ± 0.0044) with the lowest value recorded in May (station 1) while the highest was recorded in January (station 2).

Conclusively, it was proved in this study that the biological significance of the increasing concentrations of heavy metals with time in the Abule-Eledu creek is a danger or risk to the ecosystem. These harmful effects may further lead to reduction in population of organisms.

ACKNOWLEDGEMENTS

The author wishes to acknowledge the support provided by the Department of Marine Sciences and University of Lagos

REFEERENCES

1. **Kusemiju, K. (1991).** Fishes, man and the aquatic environment. Inaugural lecture series, University of Lagos Press. 35pp
2. **Nwankwo, D.I. and Akinsoji, A. (1992).** Epiphyte community of water hyacinth, *Eichhornia crassipes* (MART) Solms in coastal waters of South Western Nigeria. *Archiv fur Hydrobiologie* **124** (4): 501-511
3. **Onyema, I.C. and Nwankwo, D.I. (2006).** The epipelagic assemblage of a polluted estuarine creek in Lagos, Nigeria. *Pollution Research.* **25**(3): 459-468
4. **Akpata, T.V.I. and Ekundayo, J.A. (1978).** Faecal pollution of the Lagos lagoon. *Nig.J.Sci.* **12**: 39-53.
5. **Fodeke, V.A. A. (1985).** Groundwater contamination by waste leachates. Ph.D. Thesis University of Benin, Nigeria. 125pp
6. **Nwankwo, D.I. (1993).** Cyanobacteria bloom species in coastal waters of South-Western Nigeria. *Archiv fur Hydrobiologie.* **90**: 533-542
7. **Oyewo, E.O. and K.N. Don-Pedro, (2003).** Influence of salinity variability on heavy metal toxicity of three estuarine organisms. *J. Nigeria Environ. Sci.*, **1**(2): 141-155.
8. **Lawson, E.O (2011)** Physico-Chemical Parameters and Heavy Metal Contents of Water from the Mangrove Swamps of Lagos Lagoon, Lagos, Nigeria. *Advances in Biological Research* **5** (1): 08-21, 2011
9. **Akintola A.A., John A.O. and Titiloye O. (1981).** Chemical composition of agricultural wastes products contaminating water sources. In proceedings of second National Conference on water pollution. Kaduna-Nigeria, December 1981 (O.I. Akinyele, J.A.I Omueti and A.M.A Imevebore,ed)198-210. Federal Ministry of Water Resources.
10. **Fodeke V.A. (1979)** Studies on heavy metals and microbial concentration of *Tilapia* sp in Lagos lagoon. (Msc. Thesis). University of Lagos. Lagos
11. **Chukwu L.O. (1991).** Studies on heavy metal contamination of Water, sediment and decapods crustaceans from River shasha. (PhD. Thesis) University of Lagos. 164pp
12. **Nwankwo, D. I. (1996).** Phytoplankton diversity and succession in Lagos lagoon, Nigeria. *Archiv fur Hydrobiologie* **135** (4): 529-542.
13. **Edmunds J. (1978).** Sea shells and molluscs found on West African Coasts and Estuaries. Ghana University Press, Accra. 146 pp.
14. **Yankson K, & Kendall M. A. (2001).** Student's guide to the seashore of West Africa. Marine Biodiversity Capacity Building in the West African Sub-region. Darwin Initiative Report 1, Ref. 162/7/451. 305p.
15. **Bouchard RW.Jr. (2004).** Guide to aquatic macroinvertebrates of the Upper Midwest. Water Resources Center, University of Minnesota, St. Paul, MN. 208 p.
16. **Victor, R. and Onomivbori, O. (1996).** The effects of urban perturbation on the benthic macroinvertebrates of a southern Nigeria stream. In: F. Schiomer Biland, (Eds). SPB Academic Publishing Amsterdam, The Netherlands, pp: 223-238.

17. **Edokpayi, C.A., R.E. Uwadiae, A.O. Asoro and A.E. Badru, (2008).** Phytomacroinvertebrates arthropods associated with the roots of *Eichhornia crassipes* (water hyacinth) in a tropical West African Lagoon. *Ecology, Environment and Conservation*, 14(2-3): 241-247.
18. **Saliu, J. K. Jr. (1989).** Aquatic insects associated with plants in two reservoirs at Ibadan, Nigeria. *Rev. Biol. Trop.*, 37(2):217 – 219.
19. **Williams, W.D. and Hynes, H.N. (1976).** The Recolonisation Mechanism of Stream Benthos. *OIKOS* 27:265-349
20. **Bailey, R.G. and Litterick, M.R. (1993).** The macroinvertebrate fauna of water hyacinth fringes in the solid swamps (River Nile, Southern Sudan). *Hydrobiologia*. **250** (2) 97-103.
21. **Bryan, C.F. (1993).** Roles of the exotic water hyacinth in the distribution and resets of macroinvertebrates in the Atchafalaya River Swamp. Aslo and SWS 1993 Annual Meeting. Abstracts. U.S.A. ASLO-SWS 1993.
22. **Victor, R. and Dickson, D.I. (1985).** Macrobenthic Invertebrates of a Perturbed Stream in Southern Nigeria. *Tropical Zoology*. 3pp
23. **Dance, K.W. and Hynes, H.B.N. (1980).** Some effect of Agricultural Land use on Stream insect communities. *Environ. Pollut. Ser. A*. 22:19-28
24. **Ademoroti L.M.A, Sridhar M.K.C. (1979)** Fluidized bed technique in physico-chemical treatment of wastewater. *J. Effluent and water treatment*. 19: 91-97.
25. **DeGregori I, Pinochet H, Arancibia M, Vidal A (1996).** Grain Size Effects on Trace Metals Distribution in Sediments from Two Coastal Areas of Chile. *Bull. Environ. Contam. Toxicol.*;Vol **57**, pp 163-170.
26. **Asia I.O. and Ademoroti M.A. (2001).** Performance of some coagulation /flocculation's in the physicochemical treatment of aluminum extrusion sludge. *Proc. Chem. Soc. Nig*, pp: 47.
27. **Simpson, W.R., (1982).** Cadmium in the marine environment. *Progressive Oceanography*, 10: 1-70.
28. **Everall, N.C., N.A.A. MacFarlane and R.W. Sedgwick, (1989).** The interactions of water hardness and pH with acute toxicity of zinc to brown trout, *S. trutta*, L. *J. Fish Biol.*, 35: 27-36.
29. **Edgington, D.N. and J.A. Robbin, (1976).** Records of lead deposition in Lake Michigan sediment since 1880. *Environmental Science Bulletin*, pp: 1142-1150.
30. **Rosental, R., (1984).** Trace element distribution chemical fractions of False Bay sediments. CSIR, South Africa, pp: 148.
31. **Kumada, H., Kimura S. and Yokote, M. (1980).** Accumulation and biological effects of Cd in rainbow trout. *Bulletin of Japanese Society of Fisheries*, 46: 97-103.
32. **Westerhagen, H. Von, V. Dethletsen and H. Rosental 1980.** Correlation between cadmium concentration in the water and tissue residue levels in Dab, *Limanda limanda*, L. and Plaice, *Pleuronectes platessa*, L. *J. Marine Biological Association of UK.*, 60: 45-58
33. **Osborne, L.L., D.R. Iredale, F.J. Wrona and R.W. Davies, (1981).** Effects of Chlorinated sewage effluents on Fish in the sheep River, Alberta. *Trans American Fisheries Society*, 110: 536-540.

34. **Norris, R.H. and Lake, P.S. (1984).** Trace metal concentrations in fish from the South Esk River, North Eastern Tasmania, Australia *Bull. Env. Cont. and Toxicolo.*, 33: 348-354.
35. **Alabaster, J.S. and Lloyds, R. (1982).** Water quality criteria for freshwater fish. Second edition, Butterworths publication, London, pp: 361.
36. **Goering, P.L., Waalkes M.P. and Klaassen, C.D. (1994).** Toxicology of metals. In Zinc supplement overdose can have toxic effects. (R. Hess and B. Schmidt, ed.)
37. **United State Environmental Protection Agency (US EPA), 2010.** List of contaminants and their maximum contaminant level (MCLs). URL: <http://water.epa.gov/drink/contaminants/index.cfm> #List. Accessed on 26-12-2010.
38. **Evans, D.W., N.H. Cutshall, F.H. Cross and D.A. Wolfe, (1977).** Manganese cycling in the Newport estuary, North Carlifonia. *Estuar. Coast. Marine Sciences*, 5: 71-80.
39. **Lovell, R.T., (1989).** Nutrition and feeding of fish. Published by Van Nostrand Reinhold New York, pp: 260.
40. **Singh J, Hewawassam H. and Moffat D. (1995).** Nigeria: Strategic options for redressing industrial pollution. Vol.1 Industry and Energy Diversion, West Central Africa Depatment. 45pp
41. **Oyenekan J.A. (1975)** A survey of Lagos lagoon benthos (With particular reference to the mollusca). (Msc.Thesis) University of Lagos Nigeria.137pp